

Next Generation Software User Experience at Eastman Kodak Company

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Background

The nature of Kodak's consumer business creates an opportunity to forge a bond with users that strengthens and leverages the unique emotional connection between their memories, important moments their in life and the Kodak products they use. The first opportunity to realise this idea is in a new major release of Kodak EasyShare software. As part of an integrated system, EasyShare software enables users to share, print, organise and edit digital pictures on a personal computer.

For many users, EasyShare software is a central point from which memories, captured with their digital cameras, are relived and shared with others. Because this application is so central to the Kodak experience, it has received new focus and attention that specifically speaks to the execution of design and user experience in a way that addresses the expectations, needs and desires of our users. Enabling this focus is the implementation of a new and robust user interface technology that provides the capability to develop and present the required objects in support of new interaction models.

The responsibility for the development and execution of user experience resides with the Corporate Design & Usability (CD&U) division of Kodak. Within CD&U, a multi-disciplinary design team was formed to address the reinvention of EasyShare software. This team consisted of individuals with expertise in interaction design, human factors, graphic design, digital photography, motion graphics, and fashion design. The process employed by the team was highly collaborative and used the unique skills of each individual. While core features and workflows were optimised, the team maintained focus on design execution and the creation of a sense of desirability for the application.

Design Case

The case for a wholesale redesign of EasyShare software arose because the application had only evolved incrementally from its original inception, often without consideration for design. That original design had been primarily focused on the functional attributes of the application, and its continued evolution was comprised by simply adding more functions. The original user interface design had been, for the most part, arbitrary. As features began to pile up, the original design had begun to fail, which was due to a lack of scalability. In many cases,

significant modifications to the user interface were often required that were never originally accounted for in the original design.

While baseline usability metrics and goals were maintained during this period, it was becoming apparent that the user interface was beginning to feel very outdated. This became increasingly apparent as competitors' products began to present similar functionality with greater effect and execution. EasyShare software was in fact very static and inflexible. It also lacked a certain appeal with the very users for whom it was intended to resonate. As the application grew, the perceived level of complexity had increased and it began to feel less approachable (*Fig. 1 – Kodak EasyShare software, previous generation*).

Being able to deliver on goals centered on ease of use and customer satisfaction required tight integration of workflow, interaction model, detailed interaction design and visual design. Given the increasing sophistication of the application and the nature of the consumer target segments that had been identified, one of the primary design goals was to actively manage the perceived complexity of the application and drive toward functional simplicity in its presentation. This was a pragmatic component of an underlying goal of reinforcing users' emotional connections to their pictures as part of the gestalt experience.

To overcome this complexity, a combination of progressive disclosure and a dynamic modality of presentation would be used. All functionality would not necessarily be bubbled up into a single view, nor would the design be restricted to a static two-dimensional plane. Depth, scale and volume (or the illusion thereof) would be used in conjunction with time-based transitions and interactions to overcome the limitations of the classic Cartesian parameters of the screen.

From an experience perspective, we needed to diverge from our competitors and eschew the notion of overt utilitarianism in software design. The team knew that we were competing for the highly limited amount of leisure time of our users. The perception of entertainment value in the activities and functions of the application were critical to reinforcing many positive behaviours for the business. The potential for repeat print orders, extensive electronic sharing and subsequent viral-like propagation of images within the Kodak system was very important. The key to driving these behaviours was to design a product that was both entertaining and emotionally engaging.

Being more emotionally engaging meant that we had to make users' pictures the center of the application's experience. The goal was to enhance the memories and the shared experiences that pictures often facilitate. This was the core of our design philosophy. In the past, the design approach had been adverse to this philosophy. The problem had often been addressed by embedding users' pictures into many different interface constructs. Moving forward, we decided that we must do the exact opposite. If possible, we would embed the user interface into the picture or into the construct of pictures and invert the model of the past.

Recognising that a picture is a memory also implies that pictures can be a nexus of communal bonds. Because of this, it was critical that the application address the basic human need to connect with one another in a compelling way. Building communities and relationships through picture sharing is critical to Kodak's future growth and success. This suggested that 'people' needed to become a well-integrated component of the application—people to whom one communicates via the sharing of pictures.

The actual design process utilised standard user-centered methodologies. Phase 1 included requirements gathering, extensive design benchmarking, trend research and user visualisations (*Fig. 2 – Consumer image board used for design inspiration*). The results of which lead to the development of a creative brief that was used to initiate design development activities in Phase 2. These activities included the creation of high-level design concepts (*Figs. 3.1 and 3.2 – Preliminary high-level concepts*) illustrating the core creative direction. Informing the design activities, a parallel track of workflow development and user testing drove the creation of wireframe designs (*Fig. 4 – Wireframe layout and control mapping*) used as constructs for mapping user interface controls used by the concept work. Refined concepts (*Fig. 5 – Intermediary design concepts*) were subject to additional testing that evaluated both design appeal and perceptual attributes.

Quantitative consumer insights were provided with regard to a number of potential design solutions with the objective of understanding what specific aspects of a given design were successful and might be leveraged for later iterations.

The previous generation, the proposed concept and three major competitors were tested. Specific screens were selected from each of the applications that were representative of analogous functionality. Some editing was done to ensure that content and core functionality

would be as consistent as possible and would not distract from the actual design execution. This included using consistent images, titles and account names. In addition, all obvious branding was removed to avoid influencing perceptual attributes.

The study itself was presented via a secure website to respondents that had been identified and screened through an interactive panel. One hundred (100) respondents were identified that met the requirements for the core consumer segments required by the business. These individuals also had to qualify as ‘design sensitive’, which meant that design played a significant role in their purchase behaviour and use preference.

The respondents viewed each of the five designs independently, and they were asked to provide commentary on specific aspects of the design they liked and specific aspects they did not like. Next, the five designs were shown to them simultaneously. Each respondent was asked to evaluate the designs in terms of how well they fit with a series of attributes that represented perceptual goals outlined originally in the creative brief. The five designs were then to be ranked in terms of overall appeal.

While the quantitative rankings provided an adequate indication of overall appeal and desirability, the real value of this type of study resided in the open-ended responses provided by the respondents. These responses were analyzed for emergent trends and subsequent root cause. Although the respondents had been screened for ‘design sensitivity’, they were not fluent in the design vernacular and often reacted to the Gestalt effect of many separate components. These reactions had to be distilled to their root cause in order to correctly anticipate and direct modifications for next the design iteration. Further design iterations and the evolution of the final concept (*Figs. 6.1, 6.2, 6.3 – Samples of final proposed design direction*) were driven by the input from this testing.

Implications and Conclusions

The design process yielded many interesting results. Phase 1 design benchmarking had focused on a survey and analysis of the best-in-class user experience within and beyond the software category. This information confirmed many design assumptions, including our drive for simplicity, the level and degree of reactivity for interface components and the use of dimensionality for many design elements.

As the design concepts evolved through the iterative development process, many common themes began to emerge that were, in part, crafted by many of the lifestyle trends that had been identified as critical to reinforcing appeal without pointing to a particular user segment. Simplicity, elegance and harmony were recurrent themes, which in our specific execution enabled the perception of ease. The key to our execution was to approach this from a distinctly ‘feminine’ perspective, which was reflective of the gender bias that was seen in our user segmentation.

The notion of being emotionally connected to our users meant manifesting design elements seen in both the ‘inspiration’ and ‘wellbeing’ trends common in North America. These both speak to a sense of luxury, sophistication and sanctuary being fostered in the modern home environment of our users. Reflecting that the home environment is fast becoming a focal point of use gives our application an obvious strategic advantage. But what is more important is that by reflecting this environment, we are able to create a sense of comfort and familiarity with the user that we hope fosters increased usage of the application and further enjoyment of their pictures/memories.

We found that ‘simplicity’, as a concept, was often problematic as we executed and tested designs. Simplicity often was associated with efficiency, and in the technological context of software, some of the concepts were often perceived as being cool and machine-like in their presentation. We sought to temper the cool efficiency of a sleeker technological approach with obvious natural overtones. This created a unique effect of two contrasting themes where obvious natural imagery mitigated an efficient and otherwise minimal design treatment. The use of natural imagery was limited to specific areas of the application where it could be used in more of an ambient effect, as opposed to relating to anything directly functional. We did not intend to interfere with any established control affordances. The intended effect was to create a more organic space that would encourage exploration and creativity.

The otherwise minimal final design execution consisted of a few key design elements. The majority of the screen structure used a simple geometry of repeated modular forms. Although these forms consisted of a very restrained color pallet, their rendering was somewhat sophisticated and depended on a high degree of subtlety where form and surface appeared to be sculpted by light. Simplicity was also maintained by leveraging an explicit visual hierarchy

of user interface objects that was defined by scale, rendering and the inherent behavioural attributes of the objects themselves. The typographic approach mirrored much of the same hierarchy where possible, the key being not to cross a perceived threshold of complexity for the integration of text on a given layout.

The most important factor in producing the desired spirit into the application was the definition and integration of dynamic behaviour across the user interface and within individual interface components. Creating a compelling and entertaining experience requires a high degree of on-screen reactivity. As we had leveraged a modular and hierarchical approach with other aspects of the design, the same approach was taken with the integration of animation. Similar rhythm and timing was maintained across multiple elements while the level of expressivity and complexity was directly related to an object's hierarchical position. Great care was taken to ensure that the expressive nature of a given object's behaviour complemented and reinforced the overall design direction. Given that design execution was so minimal, this expressive reactivity was viewed as the final element that would bring life to what had once been an otherwise lifeless application.

Many, if not all, of the design topics discussed are still secondary to the users' direct experience with their pictures, but the significant improvements to the user interface, which this case represents, can only facilitate the ongoing bond between users and the cherished memories that their pictures represent.